

USE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN PRIMARY CLASS MUSIC LITERACY LESSONS

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Annotation: In the article, the analysis of ideas and pedagogical processes related to the achievement of the effectiveness of the lesson through the use of interactive methods in primary grade music literacy lessons is highlighted. At the same time, the use of innovative methods, including musical games, role-playing games, working in groups and methods of developing music literacy with the help of modern technologies, was discussed from a practical and theoretical point of view. The author revealed the role of interactive methods in music education and its importance in improving the quality of education.

Keywords: school, music literacy lessons, student, musical factors, interactive methods, singing, theoretical literacy, types of activities, educational activities.

Today, elementary music literacy classes in general education schools serve as the most important means of education for students' intellectual, physical and aesthetic development. In this sense, the use of interactive educational methods, which are considered the basis of modern education, in the organization of music literacy classes rich in content, quality and efficiency, helps a skilled teacher to achieve his goal. Conveying to students the role of interactive methods in the acquisition of musical knowledge, the importance of attracting students' attention, increasing the creative approach, and their effective use in lessons is evidence of the professional competence of a music teacher. Also, creating an interesting and active learning environment in music classes through new methods, using methods aimed at students' mutual exchange of ideas and the development of their independent work skills, meets the requirements of today's modern education.

The formation of the general musical culture of students in primary school "musical literacy" classes of general education schools depends on many factors, where listening to music, singing, and theoretical literacy (acquiring theoretical information) occupy the main place. It would not be wrong to say that educational activities are expressed through the use of interactive methods in conducting these musical activities. Because the studied musical knowledge and information about it are delivered to students through interactive methods. In this process, concepts and descriptions are given directly to theoretical information.

First of all, the tasks of forming the theoretical literacy and practical performance skills of the students, which are set before the primary grade music literacy classes, are, first of all, the knowledge at the level of being able to fully perceive music, to be able to express one's attitude to it by analyzing musical works of various genres and styles (musical-artistic taste), to understand the ideological-artistic content of the work, to sing and perform it, it requires training to acquire skills and qualifications.

In the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Development Strategy for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan", the priority tasks of "further improvement of the continuous education system, increasing the opportunities of quality education services" are defined [1], in this regard, the development of interactive methods in education and the research of the scientific and methodological aspects of their introduction into the school education process are of great importance. The technological approach to education, appropriate use of modern interactive method tools are factors that actively influence pedagogical processes and ensure their effectiveness and success.

In relation to all the links of the education system where music is taught as a subject, music education in secondary schools is significantly different from the teaching of other subjects in terms of its organization, method and content (subject). This uniqueness is expressed in the organization of the music lesson primarily on the basis of interactive methods that are logically related to each other, aimed at clarifying the main topic of the lesson and the goals and tasks.

Interactive methods, according to pedagogical goals, tasks, and organization, are aimed at revealing the content and essence of the main topic of the lesson, as well as ensuring the quality and efficiency of the lesson, making it interesting and meaningful, and in the end, they serve to form the musical culture of students. While the interactive methods conducted during the lesson are in the form of independent processes, carrying them out in an integral relationship with each other stems from the specific laws of teaching this subject [3]. Singing in music lessons, music literacy, listening to music in elementary grades, rhythmic accompaniment to music in addition to playing on children's musical instruments create a wide opportunity for students to thoroughly master musical theoretical knowledge, skills related to practical performance, knowledge with interest and passion.

Depending on the content, topic, and nature of the lesson, an interactive method may come to the fore. However, the structure of the lesson is mainly determined by theoretical knowledge of the subject and practical performance. During the lesson, the students acquire musical knowledge thoroughly through interactive methods.

For example, in the process of listening to music, they get acquainted with information such as the ideological and artistic content of the music, its authors, the period of its creation, the style of performance, which local style it is, the composer, the product of the composer's creativity, the artistic content, genre, tonality, measure, and form by performing interactive methods. This serves to form students' general musical and musical-theoretical literacy.

In the process of practical performance of the lesson, i.e., singing (in a choir), students need to be aware of notation, dynamic signs, conducting rules in order to acquire the skills of vocal-choir singing. The theoretical knowledge included in the program and textbook in the activity of music literacy ensures that students acquire the necessary knowledge, skills, and abilities in the field of music, in a word, the culture of music competently and holistically.

We can demonstrate the organization of music lessons within the mentioned interactive methods in the following examples:

Online platforms (for example, musical rhythm exercises, interactive games for learning notes) can be used to improve music literacy with the help of interactive methods and modern educational technologies. These methods of teaching music engage students, focus their attention, and make learning fun through play. For example: in the "role playing" method, encourage students to imagine themselves as musical characters or instruments. For example, students can play different musical roles (conductor, singer, composer) and learn more about different aspects of music. This method allows students to create and express themselves.

The "Collaborative learning" method is to divide students into groups and allow them to participate in performing musical works, creating musical compositions or conducting music lessons together. This gives students an opportunity to learn from each other and exchange ideas.

The "interactive presentation" method consists of conducting music lessons using a smart board or an interactive screen. For example, teaching students about musical terms, notes, or pieces of music and then analyzing them through interactive questions can further improve students' musical literacy.

In addition, through the use of video and audio materials, it is possible to increase the literacy of students by listening and seeing musical works, to encourage students to analyze musical works, to study their structure, to feel and understand music through dances or movements suitable to music, using the integration of music and movement. Interactive methods related to dance and movements develop not only literacy, but also motor skills in elementary school students.

It can be seen that the scope of educational and educational activities performed during one lesson is quite wide, for this the teacher's consideration of time and effective use of time plays an important role.

Organizing a music lesson in this way, i.e. in a combination of interactive methods, has an effective effect on students' acquisition of musical-theoretical knowledge and practical performance skills. Therefore, it is necessary for a music teacher to master the organizational-pedagogical features of a music lesson and the methodology of the lesson.

- ✓ In general, when the pedagogical goals and tasks set in the music lesson, musical activities are carried out in a coherent whole, the process of formation of musical-theoretical knowledge, understanding and necessary skills and qualifications of students is effective.
- ✓ The following factors develop in this process:
 - ✓ Develops musical abilities;
 - ✓ An increase in the skills of music perception is achieved;
 - ✓ Development of vocal-choir singing skills;
 - ✓ Elementary theoretical rules of music are studied;
 - ✓ Getting to know different genres and styles of folk music (folklore, classical, status), modern (pop, vocal, choir, ensemble, orchestra, symphonic music, opera, ballet) and gaining a certain understanding and imagination about them;
 - ✓ Rhythmic accompaniment to music; By taking actions in accordance with it, it creates the ground for the development of executive abilities;
 - ✓ In the process of mastering musical-theoretical knowledge, creative thinking and musical culture in general are formed in the personality of the student.
 - ✓ By means of the ideological and artistic content of musical works, it is possible to form a musical worldview in accordance with the national idea and ideology, and implement aesthetic and moral education in young students [3]. This is important because of the content and essence of the demands and tasks set before modern education

In accordance with the didactic principles of pedagogy, each lesson should be considered as a part of the education and training system. In this case, educational tasks should not be considered as a secondary factor that complements the educational process. Therefore, this work forms a dialectic unity with education. G. Neygauz expressed the tasks of the pedagogic musician in the educational influence on the student and wrote: "Making the student smarter, more sensitive, more honest, fairer is a task that can be implemented, even if it cannot be fully implemented, it is always a dialectically justified task based on the laws of our time and the art itself." [4]

In conclusion, the use of interactive methods in elementary music literacy classes serves to deepen students' musical knowledge, increase their interest and

participation in lessons, develop a creative approach, work in groups, learn from each other, and express their opinions freely, and creates pedagogical opportunities.

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